

Serbian Biochemical Society
Eighth Conference
with international participation

University of Novi Sad – Rectorate Hall
16.11.2018. Novi Sad, Serbia

“Coordination in Biochemistry and Life”

Enzymes as active pharmaceutical ingredients in registered drugs in Serbia

Nemanja Todorović*, Mladena Lalić-Popović, Nebojša Pavlović, Svetlana Goločorbin-Kon, Vesna Tepavčević, Jelena Čanji, Katarina Jeremić

Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

*e-mail: nemanja.todorovic007@gmail.com

Enzymes represent common therapeutic targets where drugs should show their effects, primarily by enzymes' inhibition. However, there are illnesses which require the use of enzymes as therapeutic agents. The number of these drugs is not large, but some of them can be used for treatment of rare illnesses (orphan drugs)¹. ATC labels for groups A, B, C, D and M have been assigned², but in Serbia enzymes as drugs there are only in ATC groups A and B (Figure 1a)³. Therapeutic enzymes can be used for treatment of: metabolic deficiencies, metabolic storage disorders, blood clots, inflammations, cancer, etc⁴. Of all enzymes registered as drugs in Serbia, 53% is intended for the compensation of digestive enzymes, 29% is indicated for genetic illnesses and 8% is intended to treat blood clots (Figure 1b)³.

Figure 1. Distribution of registered drugs by ATC groups in Serbia (left). (b) The indications of enzyme therapy in Serbia (right).

The production of these drugs is very demanding from a pharmaceutical-technological standpoint, since they are active pharmaceutical ingredients which are obtained from living cells⁴. Enzyme sources used as APIs in medicines registered in Serbia can be seen in Figure 2. Because of protein structure and bad pharmacokinetics, oral forms should be gastro-resistant, and whenever possible they are administered parenterally, although this application carries certain risks due to the possibility of serious side effects. Pharmaceutical forms of these drugs in Serbia are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. The origin of enzymes in registered drugs in Serbia

Figure 3. Number of individual pharmaceutical forms of enzymes in Serbia

Enzymes have the potential to increase therapeutic use. The result of this descriptive study is an insight into the current state - an overview of the number and characteristics of drugs that have enzymes as API.

Acknowledgement

This study was supported by The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia (project OI 172058).

References

1. Kanters TA, Hakkaart L, Rutten-van Mólken MP, Redekop WK. Access to orphan drugs in western Europe: can more systematic policymaking really help to avoid different decisions about the same drug? *Expert Rev Pharmacoecon Outcomes Res* 2015;15:557-9.
2. WHO Collaborating Centre for Drug Statistics Methodology. ATC/DDD Index 2018. [Online]. 2018. Available at: https://www.whocc.no/atc_ddd_index/. [10.10.2018.].
3. Agencija za lekove i medicinska sredstva. Pretraživanje humanih lekova. [Online]. (updated 10.10.2018.). Available at: <https://www.alims.gov.rs/ciril/lekovi/pretrazivanje-humanih-lekova/>. [10.10.2018.].
4. Kunamneni A, Ogaugwu C, Goli D. Enzymes as therapeutic agents. In: *Enzymes in Human and Animal Nutrition*, Academic Press, Cambridge, 2018, pp. 301-12.